

Managing flies, the other major insect pollinators

Warrick R. Nelson [0000-0001-6695-0533](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6695-0533)
Independent researcher, Christchurch, New Zealand

Abstract

Flies (Diptera) have been shown to be valuable, prolific and highly effective plant pollinators, yet they are essentially absent from both popular and scientific literature.

This narrative review focuses initially on the known crop-pollinating aspects of flies. Secondly we consider how they do, or could, fit into a functional/commercial landscape, currently dominated by honey bees, as on-call pollinators. Thirdly, we focus on the perceptual and practical steps required for commercial benefit from fly pollinators. We highlight various fly and crop combinations, the environmental circumstances suitable to support crop production, and the means of ensuring a reliable source of flies to replace or complement honey bee pollination practices. Finally, some suggestions are offered for research activities towards enabling the use of flies as pollinators in commercial crops.

Introduction

Crop pollination by insects has become almost entirely focused on bees, specifically the European honey bee (*Apis mellifera* L.) (Batra 1995, Westerkamp & Gottsberger 2000, Kleijn et al. 2015, Skaldina & Blande 2025, Ellis et al. 2025). This perception has begun to shift in recent years, towards both other bee species (Nelson et al. 2022) and recognition of the role of non-bee insects (Howlett et al. 2013, Rader et al. 2016, Osterman et al. 2021b, Howlett et al. 2023). Within these non-bee insect species, flies (Diptera) have remained largely relegated to a status of interesting, but unimportant (Orford et al. 2015). This is a serious oversight as, beyond biodiversity in itself, diversity of pollination functions and abilities indicates an important role of many fly species for crop pollination (Rader et al. 2016, Cook et al. 2020b).

We can recognise three major factors contributing to this general lack of interest and awareness in flies as effective crop pollinators.

- Firstly, the honey bee industry has a very strong economic basis separate from a pollination role. Honey bees are essentially farmed animals, providing various valuable end products, not least honey. They can deliver an important service of providing a very large number of insects for crop pollination purposes, which can also be readily moved from crop to crop as the flowering season progresses (Galbraith et al. 1933, Rollin & Garibaldi 2019, Maicelo-Quintana et al. 2024).
- Secondly, there is currently no real means of providing any species of flies as “on-call” insect pollinators when required. Direct population management and provision would increase reliability of their pollination services to commercial crops.

- Thirdly, the value placed on certain insects is often based simply on learned perceptions, rather than any real evidence. The value of flies as pollinators is commonly downgraded since there are far fewer insects visible and active compared with honey bees, especially near the bee hives. Limited knowledge by farmers and pollination researchers of the different flower-visiting activities of flies and bees also limits an appreciation of the complementary role of these insect pollinators.

This narrative review aims to tackle these three points with a view to shifting the perception of flies as pollinators from ignorance or vague awareness, to take their place as a valued resource supporting economic crops that require insect pollination services. Further, we offer some research activities that are needed to progress the on-call potential of flies as crop-pollinators.

Evidence for pollination activity

In both popular lore (Prendergast et al. 2021) and research programmes, it is clearly bees (honey and sometimes bumble) and butterflies that spring to mind as pollinators (Ssymank et al. 2008, Rader et al. 2016, Smith & Saunders 2016, Osterman et al. 2021b, Requier et al. 2023, Lau et al. 2023, Blakeman et al. 2023, Date et al. 2024, Souther et al. 2024). In their eight country population survey asking about the importance of insects as pollinators and their like/dislike status of these insects, there is a clear correlation of positive attitudes with expectation of pollinator importance. Of the six insect groups mentioned, honey bees were rated the most liked and most important, and flies (in general) the least (Date et al. 2024). This may well reflect the greater species diversity as flower visitors (pollinators) across crops, with Lepidoptera and Hymenoptera being very dominant and visually prominent, and Diptera being a relatively small proportion (Sowa et al. 2025).

Both the recent USGS pollinator science strategy and the EU pollinator monitoring scheme focus primarily on bee species and cover butterflies more than flies (Otto et al. 2025) (Potts et al. 2024). A recent comprehensive analysis of pollination ecology research “reveals a continued focus on bee research, particularly honey bees” (Rahimi & Jung 2025).

Commercial growers are often strongly biased against fly species in their recognition of insect pollinators important to their crops (Osterman et al. 2021a) (Figure 1). This shows clear knowledge and expectation differences across pollination-dependent fruit crops, with a strong bias towards honey bees, then native bees, and lastly flies. However, note the marked difference in fly pollination perception between avocado growers in New Zealand and Australia (Figure 1 A and B).

Strong statements like “Diptera are the second most important order among flower-visiting (anthophilous) and flower-pollinating insects worldwide” (Larson et al. 2001), or “Flower flies are one of the most important groups of pollinators worldwide” (Gervais et al. 2018) appear to have had little effect on the recognition of flies as pollinators. “Don't forget the flies” (Raguso 2020) focused particularly on the ecological value of pollination by flies, as did “Flies (Diptera) are one of the most important groups of insect pollinators” (Robertson et al. 2020). One reason given for the general lack of recognition of the

importance of fly pollinators could be probably because they are difficult to identify and assumed to be unimportant (Orford et al. 2015, Rader et al. 2016).

Figure 1: Farmer perceptions of pollinator importance in various insect categories. Re-presented data from Osterman et al, 2021b.

In spite of this general neglect, there is indeed a considerable literature of plant pollination by flies (Drabble & Drabble 1917, Irvin et al. 1999, Mitra & Banerjee 2007, Mehrabi & Ssymank 2008, Ssymank et al. 2008, Rader et al. 2009, Ssymank & Kearns 2009, Inouye et al. 2015, Orford et al. 2015, Arcaya et al. 2017, Stavert et al. 2018, Klecka et al. 2018, Rader et al. 2020, Doyle et al. 2020, Cook et al. 2020b, Robertson et al. 2020, Rangel et al. 2023, Date et al. 2024). Flies have also been reported as pollinators of specific crops (Table 1).

Table 1: Some crops known to be pollinated by fly species. Note that many studies consider all flower visiting insects as likely pollinators.

Crop types	Reference
Almond	(Klein et al. 2012, Henselek et al. 2018, Sisterson et al. 2020)
Apple and pear	(Kendall & Solomon 1973, Quinet & Jacquemart. 2017, Miñarro & García 2018, Sonoda et al. 2022, Barahona-Segovia et al. 2023, Nakamura et al. 2023, Okamoto et al. 2024, Mupepele et al. 2025)
Avocado	(Eardley & Mansell 1996, Can-Alonzo et al. 2005, Pérez-Balam et al. 2012, Mehmood et al. 2015, Carabalí-Banguero et al. 2018, Dymond et al. 2021, Okello et al. 2021, Osterman et al. 2021b, Sagwe et al. 2022, Toukem et al. 2023, Cook et al. 2023, Dymond et al. 2025a, Cook et al. 2025)
Blueberry	(Cook et al. 2020a)
Buckwheat	(Akter et al. 2023, Timberlake et al. 2024, Chen et al. 2024)
Cacao	(Groeneveld et al. 2010, Forbes & Northfield 2016)
Caraway	(Toivonen et al. 2022, Kilian et al. 2023)
Cherry	(Eeraerts et al. 2019, Eeraerts 2022)
Chicory	(Prokop et al. 2021)
Cotton	(Cusser et al. 2021)
Cucurbits	(Kabota et al. 2025)
Cranberry	(Gervais et al. 2018)
Kiwifruit	(Miñarro & Twizell 2015, Broussard et al. 2022, Nayak et al. 2022, Howlett et al. 2022b)
Macadamia	(Tavares et al. 2015, Howlett et al. 2015, Njue et al. 2023)
Mango, open orchards and covered crops	(Anderson et al. 1982, Singh 1997, Dag & Gazit 2000, Sung et al. 2006, Dag 2009, Carvalheiro et al. 2010, Huda et al. 2015, Saeed et al. 2016, Alqarni et al. 2017, Sánchez et al. 2018, Cabrera-Asencio & Meléndez-Ackerman 2021, Sánchez et al. 2022b, 2022c, Finch et al. 2023, Marcacci et al. 2023, Sánchez et al. 2024, Ahmad et al. 2025)
Oilseed rape	(Jauker & Wolters 2008, Jauker et al. 2012, Phillips et al. 2018, Toivonen et al. 2019)
Safflower	(Shao et al. 2012)
Seed production - carrot, celery, fennel, onion and other arable crops	(Langridge & Goodman 1975, Howlett et al. 2005, Clement et al. 2007, Saeed et al. 2008, Sajjad & Saeed 2010, Howlett 2012, Howlett et al. 2016, 2017, Saunders & Rader 2019, Sahib et al. 2020, Sánchez et al. 2022a, Toikkanen et al. 2022, Davis et al. 2023c)
Strawberry	(Nye & Anderson 1974, Albano et al. 2009b, 2009a, Hodgkiss et al. 2018, Herrmann et al. 2019, Villa-Galaviz et al. 2023, Blareau et al. 2023, Richard et al. 2024)
Watermelon	(Sánchez et al. 2022d)
Zingiber (ginger)	(Arumugam et al. 2021)

Flies as pollinators: challenging perceptions

A common general public view of flies is that they are ‘filthy’ and ‘nuisances’ (Rustiawan & Rifai 2022, Nayduch et al. 2023), with well-deserved opprobrium in many cases. But, as in the case of wasps (Brock et al. 2021, Borchardt et al. 2024), pest species within a large and varied grouping of insects may tarnish the reputation of the entire group. Oddly, human deaths from bee stings, while well known about (Ferreira et al. 2012, Feás et al. 2022), have not reduced the positive general perception of honey bees.

The enduring negative view is borne out by a broad negative perception (Date et al. 2024)(Figure 2). Note that hover flies in this study were specifically separated from flies generally, probably because they are strong mimics of honey bees (Holloway 1976)(Figure 2) or bumble bees (Heal 1982, Edmunds & Reader 2014).

*Figure 2: The drone fly, *Eristalis tenax*, is geographically widespread and easily mistaken for a honey bee.*

As a contrast, positive aspects of flies do exist, some in unusual ways (Heath 1982, McCune et al. 2023). They can convert waste organic material to valuable protein substrates, such as the black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens* L.) for human and animal feed (Varelas 2019, Montanari et al. 2021). Some flies are also known for weed or insect pest control, generally in their larval stage (Rotheray 1993, Dunn et al. 2020, Pekas et al. 2020, Reynolds et al. 2024, Burgio et al. 2024). But potentially the greatest of these, hiding in plain sight, is their role in crop pollination as already detailed.

Hairy flies, for example many syrphids, are recognised for carrying large numbers of pollen grains, often similar in number to honey bees ((Kendall & Solomon 1973, Stavert et al. 2016, 2018, Földesi et al. 2021, Zheng et al. 2024)).

In spite of crop pollination research being strongly biased towards bees, there is a small but growing literature, not just of their potential for crop pollination, but also the circumstances affecting their presence and numbers in and near crops. Many of these are demonstrated in Table 2 and the instances of managing these populations in crops and landscapes more generally.

Table 2: Flies can be more effective pollinators in certain circumstances.

Environmental circumstances where flies provide pollination advantages	
Flies more important at high latitude and high altitude, and cooler diurnal or seasonal conditions	(Arroyo et al. 1982, Rader et al. 2013, Tiusanen et al. 2016, Sakurai & Takahashi 2017, McCabe & Cobb 2021, Klausen 2022, Cirtwill et al. 2022, Zoller et al. 2023)
Dioecious and commercial hybrid species	(Heath 1982, Borkent & Harder 2007, Howlett 2012, Inouye et al. 2015, Gaffney et al. 2018, Sánchez et al. 2022a, 2022d, Tatsuno et al. 2023)
Greenhouse or other enclosed environments	(Faulkner 1978, Heath 1982, Gladis 1997, Schittenhelm et al. 1997, Jarlan et al. 1997, Clement et al. 2007, Ssymank et al. 2008, Sánchez et al. 2018, 2022b, 2022c, Shimomae et al. 2022, Li et al. 2023, Li & Wu 2023, Gonzalez et al. 2024)

The biggest contribution to recognition of flies for this purpose will be the demonstration of adequate numbers for effective pollination and being able to deliver these numbers when required. Flies as complementary pollinators have the potential to overcome the constraints evident in honey bee provision and pollination services (Williams et al. 2010, Aizen et al. 2022, Siviter et al. 2023). The development of management techniques will serve to close the gap in reliability of a deliberate, adequate and timely use of flies for specific crop pollination needs.

Insect pollinator management

The importance of managing a population can be seen by the current bias towards honey bees as near-universal pollinating insects because they are easily managed and in large numbers. As Batra (1995) noted, this bias occurs in spite of honey bees sometimes being maladapted for the purpose. Further, an overabundance of honey bees in crops can displace other pollinators (Westerkamp & Gottsberger 2000).

The perceived loss of pollinator diversity and populations focuses primarily on bee species, with only minor attention to all other flower visiting insects and flies often ignored (Potts et al. 2010, Leather 2018, Cardoso et al. 2020, Vasiliev 2021, Zattara & Aizen 2021, Cuevas et al. 2021, Dicks et al. 2021, Fijen et al. 2022, Nath et al. 2023). Clearly there is some controversy over these claims (Hodge 2020, Saunders et al 2020, Aizen et al 2022). Regardless of this controversy, some greater emphasis on fly pollinators and specifically some degree of managing populations will ameliorate regions where there is indeed a dearth of bee pollinators. The idea of functional crop pollinator diversity rather than simply taxonomic diversity is important (Kleijn et al 2021). Strategies are being developed to promote functionally diverse insect pollinator populations within intensive agri-landscapes, by means of carefully designing semi-natural habitats (Schirmel et al 2018, Howlett et al. 2021, 2022b, 2023, van Steenis 2023).

Management of insects for pollination can cover many degrees of effort. This may entail efforts to control any or all of reproduction, growth and survival through human practices (Rader et al. 2020, Argueta-Guzmán et al. 2023).

Within the category of managed insects, we have different degrees of control over population development, placement and potentially presence within a crop (Table 3).

Table 3 Broad categories of insect management style and examples of current activities.

Management intensity	Description	Example
High	Completely managed maintenance and provision of adults moved to the pollination-requiring site.	Current managed honey bee hives and bumble bee hives. Artificially reared species with adults released to the crop, generally flies.
Medium	Active provision of nesting, breeding and food resources as appropriate for the species.	Provision of artificial breeding and food resources such as “stink pots” and swamp conditions near or in the crop.
Low	Simple but otherwise largely provision of food resources near a crop, sometimes also breeding sites.	Suitable nesting sites for wild bees such as bare soil areas for soil-nesting bees, floral strips and seminatural habitat, especially that providing food provision such as for aphidophagous syrphid flies.

High intensity management is essentially the artificial, centralised management of a population. Some fly species have been reared artificially (Pascacio-Villafán & Cohen 2023), including for provision of pollination services, such as crop breeding, especially within enclosed spaces (Faulkner 1978, Jarlan et al. 1997, Westerkamp & Gottsberger 2000, Clement et al. 2007, Leroy et al. 2010, 2010, Huang et al. 2011, Kendall et al. 2021, Osterman et al. 2021a, Sánchez et al. 2022a, Shimomae et al. 2022, Li & Wu 2023, Upchurch et al. 2023, Gonzalez et al. 2024). Species within Calliphoridae and Syrphidae have a long history of being cultured, especially for research purposes (Dolley et al. 1933, Vinogradova 2009, Pfiester & Kaufman 2009, Howlett & Gee 2019, Ichikawa et al. 2020) or Cecidomyiidae for pest biocontrol (Fratoni et al. 2020) and as animal feed ingredients (Morales-Ramos et al. 2024). Very large scale production of flies is required for eradication of pest species via the sterile insect technique, such as used successfully for screw-worms (Graham & Dudley 1959, Lindquist et al. 1992).

A **medium intensity management** option could involve actively breeding flies in or near the crop (Howlett & Gee 2019, Howlett et al. 2022b). We believe this to be a good practical option for many common mass-flowering crops where fly pollination is particularly advantageous. The reasons for this opinion are enlarged on below under “Practical steps to introducing managed fly pollinators”. Migratory or broad regional exploratory behaviour supports both blow and hover fly species to this management option (Gao et al. 2020, Hawkes et al. 2024, Wittische et al. 2024, Reynolds et al. 2024). Provision or accessibility of pollen resources is important to maintain flower-visiting insect presence. In addition to the traditional mass-flowering crops and floral strips, grasses and other wind-pollinated plants may contribute the required protein source for many insects, including flies (Saunders 2018).

A **low intensity management** option may be used, as has also been suggested for many bee species (Sheffield 2013, Nelson et al. 2022, Davidson & Howlett 2023). Provision of semi-natural habitats in the landscape enhances syrphid presence (Jönsson et al. 2015, 2015, Schirmel et al. 2018, Eeraerts et al. 2021, Howlett et al. 2023, Eeraerts 2023, 2023, Fijen et al. 2024, 2024, Alarcon-Segura et al. 2025). These habitats primarily focus on influencing natural populations to come to, or remain, in the crop by means of supplying a stimulus for egg-laying. Different examples of this depend on the species desired and therefore will differ according to the lifecycle requirements. For example, supplying carcasses for calliphorids (Finch et al. 2023), or temporary artificial wetlands for syrphid species with rat-tail larvae (Howlett & Gee 2019, Davis et al. 2023b). Population growth in these systems is not necessarily a requirement. Clearly there are fly species options where the various diet and habitat needs can be provided to develop and maintain a population for crop pollination purposes (Davis et al. 2023a).

Choice of species

There is strong evidence that a number of fly species provide generalist pollination services for many common arable and orchard crops (Table 1). Blow flies (Calliphoridae) and hover flies (Syrphidae) are both entirely amenable to management and (research) culture techniques. In general, this involves providing adequate breeding, larval development and adult food sites within physiological flying distances of the crop requiring pollination.

Blow flies are easy to culture (Mackerras 1933, Ssymank et al. 2008, Chaudhury et al. 2015, Saeed et al. 2016, Ichikawa et al. 2020, Rogers et al. 2020, Cook et al. 2024b, 2024a) and the provision of carrion to attract females to breed influences the number of flies in the crop (Brown et al. 2019, Cusser et al. 2020, Pain 2021, Finch et al. 2023). Although there is the obvious potential for unintentional detrimental livestock effects and offensive smells, there are, or have been, a number of commercial suppliers of pupae for release as pollinators, listed by Cook et al. (2020b) and Ssymank et al. (2008). A cautionary note is that blow flies may have a detrimental effect on honey bee flower-visiting behaviour, resulting in reduced seed set compared with pollination by bees alone (Gagic et al. 2021).

Syrphid flies with rat-tailed maggots, commonly known as drone flies, and *E. tenax* in particular (Howlett & Gee 2019, Doyle et al. 2020), have many advantages to favour them for management of general crop pollination. A wetland habitat, natural or artificial, provides non-floral resources for the larval stages (Begosh et al. 2020, Oldham et al. 2025). These species are widely present in cropping regions of the world (Buckton 1895). Related species with similar larval habitat requirements to *E. tenax*, such as *Eristalinus* (Sánchez et al. 2022d, Davis et al. 2023c) and *Parhelophilus* (Babošová & Porhajašová 2024) are often also geographically widely distributed and can develop large populations. It is clearly easy to provide a breeding site, permanent or temporary, to suit the crop and seasonal requirements and have shown particular value in commercial hybrid vegetable seed production (Howlett & Gee 2019, Howlett et al. 2022a, Davis et al. 2023b). In addition, the adults are not nuisance species for livestock or urban environments. Central culturing for research (Nicholas et al. 2018), or crop pollination purposes

already exists (Gladis 1997, Polyfly 2019). Care appears to be needed to maintain genetic diversity in captive populations (Francuski et al. 2014). The genome of *E. tenax* is now available (Hawkes & Wotton 2021) and might lead to specific breeding targets, such as adult morphological traits (Holloway 1993, Francuski et al. 2014, Ludoški et al. 2023).

Thus a first commercial-scale management attempt will likely need to focus on drone flies, with blow fly management developed more cautiously. Other families of flies known to pollinate arable crops, for example sarcophagids, may provide a similar management option, particularly for focusing on pollination at times of year when other species are less commonly present (Howlett et al. 2016).

Practical steps to introducing flies as managed pollinators

A broad survey of farmer understanding of the value of flies, native bees and honey bees as pollinators of their perennial fruit crops indicates some interesting differences in view by crop and by country (Osterman et al. 2021b)(Figure 1). Similarly, a survey of European cherry orchardists noted recognition of flies alongside bees, but largely discounted them as providing a pollination service in favour of non-managed bee species (Eraerts 2022).

This is an important step towards introducing management options of flies for crop pollination as clearly some growers are already largely aware of flies in their crops, although on the whole they are likely to regard them as of limited pollination effectiveness. However, this existing awareness can be built on to begin to integrate practices of fly management for pollination purposes. Opening a discussion of what these management practices might look like is necessary, as the initial expectation is commonly that management will be similar to the existing honey bee hive placement within crops. Specific tools to effect practice change may prove adaptable to this task (Nelson et al. 2024, Dymond et al. 2025b).

Developing simple, reliable, cheap, effective and socially acceptable management options for fly pollination services will greatly build resilience and security of insect pollinator provision for crops. Demonstrating these through farmer/orchardist-participant activities (Howlett et al. 2022a, 2022b, Howlett 2023) has shown greater practice change and active participation rather than the more common academic view of only suggesting change in academic publications or via government policy interventions on their own. Explicitly soliciting active participation in the processes of developing, provisioning and demonstrating effectiveness is a key component (Nelson et al. 2024). There is clearly a general interest within both rural and urban populations in insect pollinator conservation (Geppert et al. 2024), so better general knowledge of the role of certain flies as pollinators may result in improved uptake of fly pollination support activities.

Fly pollinators are complementary to bee pollination activities

Bee biodiversity decline (Batra 1995)(Potts et al. 2010, van der Sluijs & Vaage 2016, Saunders et al. 2018, 2020, Cardoso et al. 2020, Vasiliev 2021, Dicks et al. 2021) and colony collapse disorder of managed honey bees (Williams et al. 2010, Brown et al. 2016) have raised concern for crop pollination provision

generally (Hristov et al. 2020). Flies can fill this emerging gap between need and provision of effective insect pollination services. Further, there are some specific circumstances where flies can provide a better pollination service (Table 2), such as during cool diurnal or seasonal conditions (Heinrich 1974, Morgan & Heinrich 1987, Howlett et al. 2013, Knop et al. 2017), or for commercial hybrid seed and dioecious crops (Faulkner 1978, Erickson et al. 1979, Evans et al. 2011, Garibaldi et al. 2013, Gaffney et al. 2019, Abbate et al. 2023). They may also be more effective in covered cropping systems where honey bee management is problematic (Evans et al. 2019, Kendall et al. 2021, Nobes et al. 2022), while the strongly selective behaviour of honey bees can be highly detrimental for F₁ hybrid seed production (Faulkner 1974).

Across agricultural and natural ecosystems it is evident that bees and flies, central and non-central place foragers respectively (Shapira et al. 2024), disperse differently within and between adjacent landscapes (Kacelnik et al. 1986, Jauker et al. 2009, 2019, Rader et al. 2011, Thyselius et al. 2018, Murail et al. 2024). They also exhibit different windows of diurnal activity (Gilbert 1985, Howlett et al. 2013, Knop et al. 2017, Karbassioon & Stanley 2023, Cook et al. 2023), thus reducing competition between insect types and providing an extended period for pollination to occur (Blareau et al. 2025). Plants flowering early in spring, thus during cooler weather, are at a particular disadvantage for successful bee pollination because bees may not yet be fully active (Stemkovski et al. 2023). Appropriate fly species can therefore also provide a complementary pollination service by providing increased functional diversity (Table 2) (Woodcock et al. 2019).

This complementary role of flies will enhance security of crop pollination provision (Rader et al. 2009, 2013, 2016, Howlett et al. 2013, Grass et al. 2016, Jeavons et al. 2020, Broussard et al. 2022).

Further research is needed to establish flies as reliable crop-pollinators

Management of pollination services by honey bees has been developed over a long period of time. Two examples are:

1. Recommendations of the number of hives/bees for various crops and measures of hive strength for pollination (Free 1993 pp 51-52),
2. Manipulation of hive foraging behaviour such as to favour foragers collecting pollen (Goodwin et al. 1991).

Some topics suggested for research

Fly provisioning

- What kind of breeding habitat is most practicable and reliable? Rat tail maggot syrphid flies, such as *E. tenax*, will breed in a wide range of wet organic materials.
- Is provision required to prevent predation of larvae (maggots) and pupae?

- How do we maintain the breeding habitat to ensure flies remain available through the flowering period?
- Will these artificial habitats require seeding with adults at the beginning of the season, especially if a certain species is desired?
- Is there potential to store pupae until required beyond the demonstrated very short term (Ichikawa et al. 2020, Campoy et al. 2020, 2022), or can they be bred in a greenhouse, or similar, to ensure numbers available for early spring release?
- What might be the effect of mass rearing on other environmental insects or ecological functions, especially if the reared species are not native?

Field behaviour and pollination verification

- How many flies are required in a crop? Since flies are not central place foragers, there is likely to be a far smaller number of individuals required as they do not have to make repetitive daily flights from flowers back to a hive. This could be disconcerting for a grower used to seeing many honey bees in the crop.
- Is there a means for growers to readily determine that a sufficient number of flies is visiting the crop flowers?
- Are flies less effective pollinators considering they are generally described as being slower flower visitors than honey bees? There is some indication that the actual pollination effect of a quick visiting pattern by honey bees may not translate to more crop yield (Celis-Diez et al. 2023).
- Do flies remain in the crop sufficiently long to provide the pollination service? A recently released Formal Model for *E. tenax* growth and environmental distribution contributes to these questions (Ziółkowska et al. 2025).
- How do the various pollinating species interact with each other? For example, some species are more aggressive and may cause others to fly more erratically, thus creating a greater opportunity for hybrid/dioecious plant pollination.
- Verification that pollination activity by the flies is effective, especially where cross-pollination is required.

Conclusion

The particular advantages that cause growers to prefer honey bees as pollinators is the presence of a large industry able to readily provide bees for pollination, plus their own familiarity with these insects, strongly influenced by both academic and popular literature. The growing demand for pollination services, especially for hybrid/dioecious crops, as well as crops grown under a cover, is emphasising the value of flies.

Without a more common recognition of the importance of various fly species in this service, their recognition and use cannot advance in terms of specific requirements or enhancing the productivity and

reliability of these services. Although there is a swing towards recognising non-honey bee crop pollination services (Reilly et al. 2024), there remains a gaping academic hole in crop pollination services of the Diptera generally. This will also entail a more general population education of the real crop pollinating insects, considering the bizarre common perception of the importance of butterflies to pollination (Althaus et al. 2021, Date et al. 2024)(Fig 2).

With examples of both calliphorid and syrphid management options, a rapid change towards confidence of reliability and efficacy of fly pollination is on the cusp of acceptance and use.

Ignorance more frequently begets confidence than does knowledge

Darwin 1871 *The Descent of Man*

Acknowledgements

Brad Howlett for contribution of Figure 1, initial discussions of concepts and reviewing an earlier draft.

Bev Nelson for reviewing for clarity of expression and grammar.

No specific funding was obtained for this review

References

- Ahmad A, Sajjad A, Khurram H and Ali M 2025 Impact of farm management practices and landscape composition on pollinator communities in mango orchards: a study from southern Punjab, Pakistan. *New Zealand Journal of Crop and Horticultural Science*: 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01140671.2025.2516613>
- Aizen MA, Garibaldi LA and Harder LD 2022 Myth and reality of a global crisis for agricultural pollination. *Ecología Austral* 32: 698–715. <https://doi.org/10.25260/EA.22.32.2.1.1875>
- Akter M, Hossain M, Rahman S, Banu M and Akhtar M 2023 Insect diversity and pollination effect on buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*) yield. *Journal of Biodiversity Conservation and Bioresource Management* 9: 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jbcbm.v9i1.66636>
- Alarcon-Segura V, Grass I, Feuerbacher A, Gonzales-Chavez A and Mupepele A-C 2025 Semi-natural habitats and their contribution to crop productivity through pollination and pest control: a systematic review. *Landscape Ecology* 40: 137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-025-02160-7>
- Albano S, Salvado E, Borges PAV and Mexia A 2009a Floral visitors, their frequency, activity rate and Index of Visitation Rate in the strawberry fields of Ribatejo, Portugal: selection of potential pollinators. Part 1. *Advances in Horticultural Science* 23: 238–245. <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/2403725>
- Albano S, Salvado E, Duarte S, Mexia A and Borges PAV 2009b Pollination effectiveness of different strawberry floral visitors in Ribatejo, Portugal: selection of potential pollinators. Part 2. *Advances in Horticultural Science* 23: 246–253. <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/2403726>
- Alqarni A, Ahmed K, Hannan M, Ghose G and Munshi J 2017 Flies for the pollination of greenhouse mango (*Mangifera indica* L., Anacardiaceae) in the subtropical Iriomote island, Japan. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Science* 43: 135–141. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jasbs.v43i1.46252>
- Althaus SL, Berenbaum MR, Jordan J and Shalmon DA 2021 No buzz for bees: Media coverage of pollinator decline. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 118: e2002552117. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2002552117>
- Anderson D, Sedgley M, Short J and Allwood A 1982 Insect pollination of mango in northern Australia. *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research* 33: 541. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AR9820541>
- Arcaya E, Pérez-Bañón C, Mengual X, Zubcoff-Vallejo JJ and Rojo S 2017 Life table and predation rates of the syrphid fly *Allograpta exotica*, a control agent of the cowpea aphid *Aphis craccivora*. *Biological Control* 115: 74–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2017.09.009>

- Argueta-Guzmán M, West M, Gaiarsa MP, Allen CW, Cecala JM, Gedlinske L, McFrederick QS, Murillo AC, Sankovitz M and Rankin EEW** 2023 Words matter: how ecologists discuss managed and non-managed bees and birds. *Scientometrics* 128: 1745–1764. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04620-2>
- Arroyo MTK, Primack R and Armesto J** 1982 Community studies in pollination ecology in the high temperate Andes of central Chile. I. Pollination mechanisms and altitudinal variation. *American Journal of Botany* 69: 82–97. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1537-2197.1982.tb13237.x>
- Arumugam N, Jayaraj VK, Subramaniam S and Appalasamy S** 2021 Evaluation on floral visitors of *Zingiber spectabile* (Zingiberaceae) at Gua Ikan, Kelantan, Peninsular Malaysia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 842: 012020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/842/1/012020>
- Babošová M and Porhajašová J** 2024 The diversity, spatial structure, and significance of the Syrphidae population in the territory of the Listové Lake Nature Reserve. *Journal of Central European Agriculture* 25: 1014–1023. <https://doi.org/10.5513/JCEA01/25.4.4318>
- Barahona-Segovia RM, Gatica-Barrios P, Durán-Sanzana V and Smith-Ramírez C** 2023 No wild bees? Don't worry! Non-bee pollinators are still hard at work: the edge effect, landscape, and local characteristics determine taxonomic and functional diversity in apple orchards. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4371927>
- Batra SWT** 1995 Bees and pollination in our changing environment. *Apidologie* 26: 361–370. <https://doi.org/10.1051/apido:19950501>
- Begosh A, Smith LM, Park CN, Mcmurry ST and Lagrange TG** 2020 Effects of wetland presence and upland land use on wild Hymenopteran and Dipteran pollinators in the rainwater basin of Nebraska, USA. *Wetlands*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-019-01244-w>
- Blakeman E, Wilson AB, Romer S, Olin E, Scott C, Popescu V and Brodie B** 2023 Passively crowdsourcing images online for measuring broad-scale fly (Diptera) floral interactions and biodiversity. *Journal of Pollination Ecology* 33: 180–193. [https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603\(2023\)724](https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603(2023)724)
- Blareau E, Gabard C, Riva C, Dajoz I and Requier F** 2025 Automated 24-h surveys of flower-visiting communities reveal temporal complementarities and overlaps among strawberry pollinators. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 62: e03727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2025.e03727>
- Blareau E, Sy P, Daoud K and Requier F** 2023 Insect-mediated pollination of strawberries in an urban environment. *Insects* 14: 877. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects14110877>
- Borchardt KE, Holthaus D, Soto Méndez PA and Toth AL** 2024 Debunking wasp pollination: Wasps are comparable to bees in terms of plant interactions, body pollen and single-visit pollen deposition. *Ecological Entomology*: een.13329. <https://doi.org/10.1111/een.13329>
- Borkent CJ and Harder LD** 2007 Flies (Diptera) as pollinators of two dioecious plants: behaviour and implications for plant mating. *The Canadian Entomologist* 139: 235–246. <https://doi.org/10.4039/n05-087>
- Brock RE, Cini A and Sumner S** 2021 Ecosystem services provided by aculeate wasps. *Biological Reviews* 96: 1645–1675. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12719>
- Broussard MA, Howlett BG, Evans LJ, McBrydie H, Cutting BT, Read SFJ and Pattemore DE** 2022 Pollinator identity and behavior affect pollination in kiwifruit (*Actinidia chinensis* Planch.). *PeerJ* 10: e12963. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.12963>
- Brown C, Varischetti B and Fowler C** 2019 Animal carcasses and their flies could be 'the new bees' as researchers try to diversify pollinators. *NT Country Hour* <https://www.abc.net.au/news/rural/2019-08-09/researchers-investigate-the-role-of-flies-in-pollination/11395604>
- Buckton GB** 1895 The natural history of *Eristalis tenax* or the drone-fly. Macmillan, London
- Burgio G, Dindo ML, Pape T, Whitmore D and Sommaggio D** 2024 Diptera as predators in biological control: applications and future perspectives. *BioControl*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10526-024-10281-2>
- Cabrera-Asencio I and Meléndez-Ackerman EJ** 2021 Community and species-level changes of insect species visiting *Mangifera indica* flowers following Hurricane María: “the devil is in the details”. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 9: 556821. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.556821>
- Campoy A, Egea-Casas O, Pérez-Bañón C and Rojo S** 2022 Effect of cold storage on the pupal development of two pollinators, *Eristalinus aeneus* and *Eristalis tenax*. *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata* 170: 110–121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eea.13117>
- Campoy A, Pérez-Bañón C and Rojo S** 2020 Intra-puparial development in the hoverflies *Eristalinus aeneus* and *Eristalis tenax* (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Journal of Morphology* 281: 1436–1445. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmor.21257>
- Can-Alonzo C, Quezada-Euán JGG, Xiu-Ancona P, Moo-Valle H, Valdovinos-Nunez GR and Medina-Peralta S** 2005 Pollination of 'Criollo' avocados (*Persea americana*) and the behaviour of associated bees in subtropical Mexico. *Journal of Apicultural Research* 44: 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00218839.2005.11101138>

- Carabalí-Banguero D, Montoya-Lerma J and Carabalí-Muñoz A** 2018 Dipterans associated to the flowering of the avocado *Persea americana* Mill cv. Hass in Cauca, Colombia. *Biota Colombiana* 19: 92–111. <https://doi.org/10.21068/c2018v19n01a06>
- Cardoso P, Barton PS, Birkhofer K, Chichorro F, Deacon C, Fartmann T, Fukushima CS, Gaigher R, Habel JC, Hallmann CA, Hill MJ, Hochkirch A, Kwak ML, Mammola S, Ari Noriega J, Orfinger AB, Pedraza F, Pryke JS, Roque FO, Settele J, Simaika JP, Stork NE, Suhling F, Vorster C and Samways MJ** 2020 Scientists' warning to humanity on insect extinctions. *Biological Conservation* 242: 108426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108426>
- Carvalho LG, Seymour CL, Veldtman R and Nicolson SW** 2010 Pollination services decline with distance from natural habitat even in biodiversity-rich areas: Sub-tropics crop pollination limitation. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 47: 810–820. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2010.01829.x>
- Celis-Diez JL, García CB, Armesto JJ, Abades S, Garratt MPD and Fontúrbel FE** 2023 Wild floral visitors are more important than honeybees as pollinators of avocado crops. *Agronomy* 13: 1722. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy13071722>
- Chaudhury MF, Chen H, Sagel A and Skoda SR** 2015 Effects of new dietary ingredients used in artificial diet for screwworm larvae (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *Journal of Economic Entomology* 108: 1429–1434. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/tov039>
- Chen Y, Zhang C and Van Der Werf W** 2024 Pollination services in the North China Plain measured using buckwheat sentinel plants; is there a deficit? *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 373: 109129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2024.109129>
- Cirtwill AR, Kaartinen R, Rasmussen C, Redr D, Wirta H, Olesen JM, Tiusanen M, Ballantyne G, Cunnold H, Stone GN, Schmidt NM and Roslin T** 2022 Stable pollination service in a generalist high Arctic community despite the warming climate. *Ecological Monographs*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecm.1551>
- Clement SL, Hellier BC, Elberson LR, Staska RT and Evans MA** 2007 Flies (Diptera: Muscidae: Calliphoridae) are efficient pollinators of *Allium ampeloprasum* L. (Alliaceae) in field cages. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 100: 131–135. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/100.1.131>
- Cook DF, Deyl RA, Mickan BS and Howse ET** 2020a Yield of southern highbush blueberry (*Vaccinium corymbosum*) using the fly *Calliphora albifrontalis* (Diptera: Calliphoridae) as a pollinator. *Austral Entomology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aen.12455>
- Cook DF, Tufail MS, Howse ET, Voss SC, Foley J, Norrish B and Delroy N** 2025 Pollination of enclosed avocado trees by blow flies (Diptera: Calliphoridae) and a hover fly (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Insects* 16: 899. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects16090899>
- Cook DF, Tufail MS and Voss SC** 2024a Can the necrophagous blow fly *Calliphora vicina* (Diptera: Calliphoridae) be reared on plant-based meal? *Insects* 15: 551. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects15070551>
- Cook DF, Tufail MS, Voss SC, Deyl RA, Howse ET, Foley J, Norrish B, Delroy N and Shivananjappa SL** 2023 Blow flies (Diptera: Calliphoridae) ability to pollinate Hass avocado trees within paired tree enclosures. *Journal of Applied Entomology*: jen.13159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jen.13159>
- Cook DF, Tufail MS, Voss SC, Howse ET and Rogers EK** 2024b Maggots cannot live on meat meal alone: production parameters for mass rearing of the ovoviparous blowfly, *Calliphora dubia* (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*: toae043. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/toae043>
- Cook DF, Voss SC, Finch JT, Rader RC, Cook JM and Spurr CJ** 2020b The role of flies as pollinators of horticultural crops: an Australian case study with worldwide relevance. *Insects* 11: 341. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects11060341>
- Cuevas E, Blancas J, Caballero J, Hinojosa-Díaz IA and Martínez-Ballesté A** 2021 Agricultural management and local knowledge: key factors for the conservation of socio-ecosystems in the face of the pollinator world crisis. *Botanical Sciences* 99: 305–320. <https://doi.org/10.17129/botsci.2659>
- Cusser S, Haddad NM and Jha S** 2021 Unexpected functional complementarity from non-bee pollinators enhances cotton yield. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 314: 107415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107415>
- Cusser S, Pechal JL and Haddad NM** 2020 Carrion increases pollination service across an urban gradient. *Urban Ecosystems*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-020-01032-z>
- Dag A** 2009 Interaction between pollinators and crop plants: The Israeli experience. *Israel Journal of Plant Sciences* 57: 231–242. <https://doi.org/10.1560/IJPS.57.3.231>
- Dag A and Gazit S** 2000 Mango pollinators in Israel. *Journal of Applied Horticulture* 2: 29–43.
- Date M, Fukano Y, Farkhary SI, Uchida K and Soga M** 2024 Beyond bees: A cross-country investigation into public perceptions of insect-mediated crop-pollination services. *Biological Conservation* 292: 110524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2024.110524>
- Davidson MM and Howlett BG** 2023 Native plants support more insect pollinator species than expected. *The Wētā* 57: 23–28. <https://weta.ento.org.nz/index.php/weta/article/view/411>

- Davis AE, Bickel DJ, Saunders ME and Rader R** 2023a Crop-pollinating Diptera have diverse diet and habitat needs in both larval and adult stages. *Ecological Applications*: e2859. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2859>
- Davis AE, Schmidt LA, Harrington S, Spurr C and Rader R** 2023b Provisioning Australian seed carrot agroecosystems with non-floral habitat provides oviposition sites for crop-pollinating Diptera. *Insects* 14: 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects14050439>
- Davis AE, Schmidt LA, Santos KCBS, Martin L, Harrington S, Rocchetti M, Hocking B, Wright D, Spurr C, Cook D and Rader R** 2023c The golden native drone fly (*Eristalinus punctulatus*) is an effective hybrid carrot pollinator that lives within Australian crop agroecosystems. *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 4: e12290. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12290>
- Dicks LV, Breeze TD, Ngo HT, Senapathi D, An J, Aizen MA, Basu P, Buchori D, Galetto L, Garibaldi LA, Gemmill-Herren B, Howlett BG, Imperatriz-Fonseca VL, Johnson SD, Kovács-Hostyánszki A, Kwon YJ, Lattorff HMG, Lungharwo T, Seymour CL, Vanbergen AJ and Potts SG** 2021 A global-scale expert assessment of drivers and risks associated with pollinator decline. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01534-9>
- Dolley WL, Hassett CC, Bowen WB and Phillis G** 1933 Culture of the drone fly, *Eristalis tenax*. *Science* 78: 313–314. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.78.2023.313>
- Doyle T, Hawkes WLS, Massy R, Powney GD, Menz MHM and Wotton KR** 2020 Pollination by hoverflies in the Anthropocene. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 287: 20200508. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2020.0508>
- Drabble E and Drabble H** 1917 The syrphid visitors to certain flowers. *New Phytologist* 16: 105–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.1917.tb07231.x>
- Dunn L, Lequerica M, Reid CR and Latty T** 2020 Dual ecosystem services of syrphid flies (Diptera: Syrphidae): pollinators and biological control agents. *Pest Management Science*: ps.5807. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.5807>
- Dymond K, Celis-Diez JL, Díaz-Siefer P, Rojas-Bravo V, Martínez-Harms J, Potts SG and Garratt MPD** 2025a Proximity to natural habitat enhances flower visitor diversity and pollination services in avocado orchards. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2025.1560802>
- Dymond K, Celis-Diez JL, Lymna-Dennis C, Rojas-Bravo V, Martínez-Harms J, Potts SG and Garratt MPD** 2025b Developing a rapid assessment tool for identifying and safeguarding pollinators: a case study from a global avocado company. *Conservation Science and Practice* 7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.70043>
- Dymond K, Celis-Diez JL, Potts SG, Howlett BG, Willcox BK and Garratt MPD** 2021 The role of insect pollinators in avocado production: A global review. *Journal of Applied Entomology*: jen.12869. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jen.12869>
- Eardley CD and Mansell MW** 1996 The natural occurrence of insect pollinators in an avocado orchard. *South African Avocado Growers' Association Yearbook* 18: 36–38.
- Edmunds M and Reader T** 2014 Evidence for Batesian mimicry in a polymorphic hoverfly. *Evolution* 68: 827–839. <https://doi.org/10.1111/evo.12308>
- Eeraerts M** 2022 Increasing wild bee richness and abundance on sequentially flowering cultivars of a pollinator-dependent crop. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 325: 107745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107745>
- Eeraerts M** 2023 A minimum of 15% semi-natural habitat facilitates adequate wild pollinator visitation to a pollinator-dependent crop. *Biological Conservation* 278: 109887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109887>
- Eeraerts M, Smagghe G and Meeus I** 2019 Pollinator diversity, floral resources and semi-natural habitat, instead of honey bees and intensive agriculture, enhance pollination service to sweet cherry. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 284: 106586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106586>
- Eeraerts M, Van Den Berge S, Proesmans W, Verheyen K, Smagghe G and Meeus I** 2021 Fruit orchards and woody semi-natural habitat provide complementary resources for pollinators in agricultural landscapes. *Landscape Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-021-01220-y>
- Ellis EE, Campbell SA and Edmondson JL** 2025 Drivers of nocturnal and diurnal pollinating insect declines in urban landscapes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 292: 20250102. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2025.0102>
- Faulkner GJ** 1978 Seed production of F₁ hybrid Brussels sprouts. *Acta Horticulturae*: 37–42. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1978.83.4>
- Feás X, Vidal C and Remesar S** 2022 What we know about sting-related deaths? Human fatalities caused by hornet, wasp and bee stings in Europe (1994–2016). *Biology* 11: 282. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology11020282>
- Ferreira RS, Almeida RAMB, Barraviera SRCS and Barraviera B** 2012 Historical perspective and human consequences of Africanized bee stings in the Americas. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part B* 15: 97–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2012.645141>

- Fijen TPM, Bishop GA, Ganuza C, Scheper J and Kleijn D** 2024 Analyzing the relative importance of habitat quantity and quality for boosting pollinator populations in agricultural landscapes. *Conservation Biology*: e14317. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.14317>
- Fijen TPM, Read SFJ, Walker MK, Gee M, Nelson WR and Howlett BG** 2022 Different landscape features within a simplified agroecosystem support diverse pollinators and their service to crop plants. *Landscape Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-022-01423-x>
- Finch J, Gilpin A-M and Cook J** 2023 Fishing for flies: testing the efficacy of “stink stations” for promoting blow flies as pollinators in mango orchards. *Journal of Pollination Ecology* 32: 79–100. [https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603\(2023\)711](https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603(2023)711)
- Földesi R, Howlett BG, Grass I and Batáry P** 2021 Larger pollinators deposit more pollen on stigmas across multiple plant species—A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 58: 699–707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13798>
- Forbes SJ and Northfield TD** 2016 Increased pollinator habitat enhances cacao fruit set and predator conservation. *Ecological Applications* 27: 887–899. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1491>
- Francuski L, Djuracic M, Ludoški J, Hurtado P, Pérez-Bañón C, Ståhls G, Rojo S and Milankov V** 2014 Shift in phenotypic variation coupled with rapid loss of genetic diversity in captive populations of *Eristalis tenax* (Diptera: Syrphidae): consequences for rearing and potential commercial use. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 107: 821–832. <https://doi.org/10.1603/EC13243>
- Fratoni S, Duarte MVA, Vangansbeke D, Wäckers FL, Dicke M and Pekas A** 2020 A bittersweet meal: The impact of sugar solutions and honeydew on the fitness of two predatory gall midges. *Biological Control* 140: 104098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2019.104098>
- Free JB** 1993 *Insect pollination of crops, 2nd edition*. Academic Press Inc. Ltd, London
- Gaffney A, Bohman B, Quarrell SR, Brown PH and Allen GR** 2018 Frequent insect visitors are not always pollen carriers in hybrid carrot pollination. *Insects* 9 (61): 15 pp. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects9020061>
- Gagic V, Kirkland L, Kendall LK, Jones J, Kirkland J, Spurr C and Rader R** 2021 Understanding pollinator foraging behaviour and transition rates between flowers is important to maximize seed set in hybrid crops. *Apidologie* 52: 89–100. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13592-020-00800-2>
- Galbraith J, Voorhies E and Todd F** 1933 Economic aspects of the bee industry. p. 118. Bulletin, Gianinni foundation of agricultural economics, Berkeley, California <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/9319539.pdf>
- Gao B, Wotton KR, Hawkes WLS, Menz MHM, Reynolds DR, Zhai B-P, Hu G and Chapman JW** 2020 Adaptive strategies of high-flying migratory hoverflies in response to wind currents. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 287: 20200406. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2020.0406>
- Geppert C, Franceschinis C, Fijen TPM, Kleijn D, Scheper J, Steffan-Dewenter I, Thieme M and Marini L** 2024 Willingness of rural and urban citizens to undertake pollinator conservation actions across three contrasting European countries. *People and Nature*: pan3.10656. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10656>
- Gervais A, Chagnon M and Fournier V** 2018 Diversity and pollen loads of flower flies (Diptera: Syrphidae) in cranberry crops. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aesa/say027>
- Gladis T** 1997 Bees versus flies? - Rearing methods and effectiveness of pollinators in crop germplasm regeneration. *Acta Horticulturae* 437: 235–238. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1997.437.25>
- Gonzalez N, Buitenhuis R and Lucas E** 2024 Comparison of two release strategies for the American hoverfly, *Eupeodes americanus*, against the green peach aphid in greenhouses: Banker plant vs. pupal release. *Crop Protection* 184: 106814. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2024.106814>
- Goodwin RM, Ten Houten and Perry JH** 1991 Feeding sugar syrup to honey bee colonies to improve kiwifruit pollen collection: a review. *Acta Horticulturae* 288: 265–269. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1991.288.40>
- Graham AJ and Dudley FH** 1959 Culture methods for mass rearing of screw-worm larvae. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 52: 1006–1008. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/52.5.1006>
- Groeneveld JH, Tschardtke T, Moser G and Clough Y** 2010 Experimental evidence for stronger cacao yield limitation by pollination than by plant resources. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics* 12: 183–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2010.02.005>
- Hawkes W and Wotton K** 2021 The genome sequence of the drone fly, *Eristalis tenax* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Wellcome Open Research* 6: 307. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17357.1>
- Hawkes WL, Menz MHM and Wotton KR** 2024 Lords of the flies: Dipteran migrants are diverse, abundant and ecologically important. *Biol. Rev.* 100: 1635–1359. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.70017>
- Heal JR** 1982 Colour patterns of syrphidae: IV. Mimicry and variation in natural populations of *Eristalis tenax*. *Heredity* 49: 95–109. <https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.1982.68>
- Heath ACG** 1982 Beneficial aspects of blowflies (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *New Zealand Entomologist* 7: 343–348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00779962.1982.9722422>

- Henselek Y, Eilers EJ, Kremen C, Hendrix SD and Klein A-M** 2018 Pollination requirements of almond (*Prunus dulcis*): combining laboratory and field experiments. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 111: 1006–1013. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/toy053>
- Herrmann JD, Beye H, De La Broise C, Hartlep H and Diekötter T** 2019 Positive effects of the pollinators *Osmia cornuta* (Megachilidae) and *Lucilia sericata* (Calliphoridae) on strawberry quality. *Arthropod-Plant Interactions* 13: 71–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11829-018-9636-7>
- Hodge S** 2020 When I'm sixty-four: long-term monitoring and the (missing?) New Zealand insect apocalypse. *The Wētā* 54: 11. <https://weta.ento.org.nz/index.php/weta/article/view/5/8>
- Hodgkiss D, Brown MJF and Fountain MT** 2018 Syrphine hoverflies are effective pollinators of commercial strawberry. *Journal of Pollination Ecology* 22: 55–66. [https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603\(2018\)five](https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603(2018)five)
- Holloway BA** 1976 Pollen-feeding in hover-flies (Diptera: Syrphidae). *New Zealand Journal of Zoology* 3: 339–350. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03014223.1976.9517924>
- Holloway GJ** 1993 Phenotypic variation in colour pattern and seasonal plasticity in *Eristalis* hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Ecological Entomology* 18: 209–217. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2311.1993.tb01092.x>
- Howlett B** 2012 Hybrid carrot seed crop pollination by the fly *Calliphora vicina* (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *Journal of Applied Entomology* 136: 421–430. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0418.2011.01665.x>
- Howlett B, Broussard MA, Bordes N, Graham S, Gee M, Davidson MM and Nelson WR** 2023 A roadmap for designing semi-natural habitat: plantings that benefit pollinators and people, not pests. *Advances in Ecological Research* 68: 91–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2023.09.006>
- Howlett B, Read S, Rolston P and Anderson F** 2022a Alternative pollinators for seed crops – drone fly mass rearing and utilisation. p. 5. Seed Industry Research Centre, Christchurch, New Zealand <http://www.far.org.nz/files/display/9629/all-herbage-and-vegetable-seed-reports.pdf>
- Howlett BG, Butler R, Nelson W and Donovan BJ** 2013 Impact of climate change on crop pollinator in New Zealand. p. 60. MPI Technical Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8051629>
- Howlett BG, Davidson MM, Logan DP, Gee M, Read SFJ and Todd JH** 2022b Designing semi-natural perennial plantings to support targeted pollinators for kiwifruit orchards. *Acta Horticulturae* 1332: 179–186. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2022.1332.24>
- Howlett BG, Davidson MM, Pattemore DE, Walker MK and Nelson WR** 2016 Seasonality of calliphorid and sarcophagid flies across Canterbury arable farms requiring pollinators. *New Zealand Plant Protection* 69: 290–295. <https://doi.org/10.30843/nzpp.2016.69.5899>
- Howlett BG, Donovan BJ, McCallum JA, Newstrom LE and Teulon DAJ** 2005 Between and within field variability of New Zealand indigenous flower visitors to onions. *New Zealand Plant Protection* 58: 213–218. <https://doi.org/10.30843/nzpp.2005.58.4275>
- Howlett BG, Evans LJ, Pattemore DE and Nelson WR** 2017 Stigmatic pollen delivery by flies and bees: Methods comparing multiple species within a pollinator community. *Basic and Applied Ecology* 19: 19–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2016.12.002>
- Howlett BG and Gee M** 2019 The potential management of the drone fly (*Eristalis tenax*) as a crop pollinator in New Zealand. *New Zealand Plant Protection* 72: 221–230. <https://doi.org/10.30843/nzpp.2019.72.304>
- Howlett BG, Nelson WR, Pattemore DE and Gee M** 2015 Pollination of macadamia: Review and opportunities for improving yields. *Scientia Horticulturae* 197: 411–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2015.09.057>
- Howlett BG, Todd JH, Willcox BK, Rader R, Nelson WR, Gee M, Schmidlin FG, Read SFJ, Walker MK, Gibson D and Davidson MM** 2021 Using non-bee and bee pollinator-plant species interactions to design diverse plantings benefiting crop pollination services 64: 45–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2020.11.002>
- Huang N, Enkegaard A, Osborne LS, Ramakers PMJ, Messelink GJ, Pijnakker J and Murphy G** 2011 The banker plant method in biological control. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences* 30: 259–278. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352689.2011.572055>
- Huda AN, Salmah MRC, Hassan AA, Hamdan A and Razak MNA** 2015 Pollination services of mango flower pollinators. *Journal of Insect Science* 15: 113. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/iev090>
- Ichikawa A, Ikeda M and Goto SG** 2020 Cold storage of diapausing larvae and post-storage performance of adults in the blowfly *Lucilia sericata* (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *Applied Entomology and Zoology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13355-020-00685-8>
- Inouye DW, Larson BMH, Ssymank A and Kevan PG** 2015 Flies and flowers III: Ecology of foraging and pollination. *Journal of Pollination Ecology* 16: 115–133. [https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603\(2015\)15](https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603(2015)15)
- Irvin NA, Wratten SD, Frampton CM, Bowie MH, Evans AM and Moar NT** 1999 The phenology and pollen feeding of three hover fly (Diptera: Syrphidae) species in Canterbury, New Zealand. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology* 26: 105–115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03014223.1999.9518182>

- Jarlan A, De Oliveira D and Gingras J 1997 Pollination by *Eristalis tenax* (Diptera: Syrphidae) and seed set of greenhouse sweet pepper. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 90: 1646–1649. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/90.6.1646>
- Jauker F, Bondarenko B, Becker HC and Steffan-Dewenter I 2012 Pollination efficiency of wild bees and hoverflies provided to oilseed rape. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology* 14: 81–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-9563.2011.00541.x>
- Jauker F and Wolters V 2008 Hover flies are efficient pollinators of oilseed rape. *Oecologia* 156: 819–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-008-1034-x>
- Jönsson AM, Ekroos J, Dänhardt J, Andersson GKS, Olsson O and Smith HG 2015 Sown flower strips in southern Sweden increase abundances of wild bees and hoverflies in the wider landscape. *Biological Conservation* 184: 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.12.027>
- Kabota SA, Tairo JC, Mwatawala MW, Majubwa RO, Abdul KB, Virgilio M, De Meyer M and Jordaens K 2025 Diversity of hoverflies and their floral visitation patterns in cultivated cucurbit crops in Morogoro, Tanzania. *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata* 173: 767–780. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eea.13583>
- Kendall DA and Solomon ME 1973 Quantities of pollen on the bodies of insects visiting apple blossom. *The Journal of Applied Ecology* 10: 627. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2402306>
- Kendall LK, Evans LJ, Gee M, Smith TJ, Gagic V, Lobaton JD, Hall MA, Jones J, Kirkland L, Saunders ME, Sonter C, Cutting BT, Parks S, Hogendoorn K, Spurr C, Gracie A, Simpson M and Rader R 2021 The effect of protective covers on pollinator health and pollination service delivery. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 319: 107556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107556>
- Kilian IC, Swenson SJ, Mengual X, Gemeinholzer B, Hamm A, Wägele W and Peters RS 2023 More complex than you think: Taxonomic and temporal patterns of plant-pollinator networks of caraway (*Carum carvi* L.). *Molecular Ecology*: mec.16943. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16943>
- Klausen L 2022 Spatio-temporal Diptera visitation to *Silene acaulis* flowers studied with time-lapse cameras in Svalbard and Greenland. MSc, The Arctic University of Norway. <https://hdl.handle.net/10.037/26982>
- Klecka J, Hadrava J, Biella P and Akter A 2018 Flower visitation by hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) in a temperate plant-pollinator network. *PeerJ* 6: e6025. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.6025>
- Kleijn D, Winfree R, Bartomeus I, Carvalho LG, Henry M, Isaacs R, Klein A-M, Kremen C, M'Gonigle LK, Rader R, Ricketts TH, Williams NM, Lee Adamson N, Ascher JS, Báldi A, Batáry P, Benjamin F, Biesmeijer JC, Blitzer EJ, Bommarco R, Brand MR, Bretagnolle V, Button L, Cariveau DP, Chifflet R, Colville JF, Danforth BN, Elle E, Garratt MPD, Herzog F, Holzschuh A, Howlett BG, Jauker F, Jha S, Knop E, Krewenka KM, Le Féon V, Mandelik Y, May EA, Park MG, Pisanty G, Reemer M, Riedinger V, Rollin O, Rundlöf M, Sardiñas HS, Scheper J, Sciligo AR, Smith HG, Steffan-Dewenter I, Thorp R, Tscharrnke T, Verhulst J, Viana BF, Vaissière BE, Veldtman R, Westphal C and Potts SG 2015 Delivery of crop pollination services is an insufficient argument for wild pollinator conservation. *Nature Communications* 6 (7414): 8 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms8414>
- Klein A-M, Brittain C, Hendrix SD, Thorp R, Williams N and Kremen C 2012 Wild pollination services to California almond rely on semi-natural habitat. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 49: 723–732. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2012.02144.x>
- Langridge D and Goodman R 1975 A study on pollination of oilseed rape (*Brassica campestris*). *Australian Journal of Experimental Agriculture* 15: 285. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EA9750285>
- Larson BMH, Kevan PG and Inouye DW 2001 Flies and flowers: taxonomic diversity of anthophiles and pollinators. *The Canadian Entomologist* 133: 439–465. <https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent133439-4>
- Lau PW, Esquivel IL, Parys KA, Hung K-LJ and Chakrabarti P 2023 The nutritional landscape in agroecosystems: a review on how resources and management practices can shape pollinator health in agricultural environments. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*: saad023. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aesa/saad023>
- Leather SR 2018 “Ecological Armageddon” - more evidence for the drastic decline in insect numbers: *Annals of Applied Biology* 172: 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aab.12410>
- Leroy PD, Verheggen FJ, Capella Q, Francis F and Haubruge E 2010 An introduction device for the aphidophagous hoverfly *Episyrphus balteatus* (De Geer) (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Biological Control* 54: 181–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2010.05.006>
- Li H and Wu K 2023 An efficient breeding method for *Eupeodes corollae* (Diptera: Syrphidae), a pollinator and insect natural enemy in facility-horticulture crops. *Horticulturae* 9: 664. <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae9060664>
- Li H, Wyckhuys KAG and Wu K 2023 Hoverflies provide pollination and biological pest control in greenhouse-grown horticultural crops. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 14: 1118388. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1118388>

- Lindquist DA, Abusowa M and Hall MJR** 1992 The new world screwworm fly in Libya: a review of its introduction and eradication. *Medical and Veterinary Entomology* 6: 2–8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2915.1992.tb00027.x>
- Ludoški J, Francuski L, Gojković N, Matić B and Milankov V** 2023 Sexual size and shape dimorphism, and allometric scaling in the pupal and adult traits of *Eristalis tenax*. *Ecology and Evolution* 13: e9907. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.9907>
- Mackerras MJ** 1933 Observations on the life-histories, nutritional requirements and fecundity of blowflies. *Bulletin of Entomological Research* 24: 353–362. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007485300031680>
- Maicelo-Quintana JL, Reyna-Gonzales K, Balcázar-Zumaeta CR, Auquiñivin-Silva EA, Castro-Alayo EM, Medina-Mendoza M, Cayo-Colca IS, Maldonado-Ramirez I and Silva-Zuta MZ** 2024 Potential application of bee products in food industry: an exploratory review. *Heliyon* 10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e24056>
- Marcacci G, Devy S, Wenzel A, Rao VS, Kumar S. S, Nölke N, Belavadi VV, Tschardt T, Grass I and Westphal C** 2023 Direct and indirect effects of urbanization, pesticides and wild insect pollinators on mango yield. *Journal of Applied Ecology*: 1365–2664.14476. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14476>
- McCabe LM and Cobb NS** 2021 From bees to flies: global shift in pollinator communities along elevation gradients. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 8: 626–124. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2020.626124>
- McCune F, Normandin É, Gervais A, Mazerolle MJ and Fournier V** 2023 Syrphid fly response to urban heat islands varies with functional traits. *Journal of Insect Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-023-00490-y>
- Mehmood K, Hussain S, Mustafa N, Bodlah I and Ahmad M** 2015 Insect pollinators visiting citrus (*Citrus limon*) and avocado (*Persea americana*) fruit trees. *Asian J Agri Biol* 3: 23–27. <https://www.asianjab.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/5-AJAB-15-139.pdf>
- Mehrabi R and Ssymank A** 2008 Species composition and flower visiting by Syrphidae (Diptera) in north-eastern Iran. *Zoology in the Middle East* 45: 73–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09397140.2008.10638309>
- Miñarro M and García D** 2018 Complementarity and redundancy in the functional niche of cider apple pollinators. *Apidologie*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13592-018-0600-4>
- Miñarro M and Twizell KW** 2015 Pollination services provided by wild insects to kiwifruit (*Actinidia deliciosa*). *Apidologie* 46: 276–285. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13592-014-0321-2>
- Mitra B and Banerjee D** 2007 Fly pollinators: assessing their value in biodiversity conservation and food security in India. *Records of the Zoological Survey of India* 107: 33. <https://doi.org/10.26515/rzsi/v107/i1/2007/159161>
- Montanari F, Pinto de Moura A and Miguel Cunha L** 2021 Insects as food and feed. *Production and Commercialization of Insects as Food and Feed* pp. 3–18. Springer International Publishing https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-030-68406-8_2
- Morales-Ramos JA, Tomberlin JK, Miranda C and Rojas MG** 2024 Rearing methods of four insect species intended as feed, food, and food ingredients: a review. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 117: 1210–1224. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/toae040>
- Mupepele A, Von Königsłow V, Bleile A, Fornoff F, Fründ J and Klein A** 2025 Plant-pollinator interactions in apple orchards from a production and conservation perspective. *Conservation Science and Practice*: e13280. <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.13280>
- Nakamura S, Taki H, Arai T, Funayama K, Furihata S, Furui Y, Ikeda T, Inoue H, Kagawa K, Kishimoto H, Kohyama M, Komatsu M, Konuma A, Nakada K, Nakamura S, Sawamura N, Sonoda S, Sueyoshi M, Toda S, Yaginuma K, Yamamoto S, Yoshida K, Yokoi T and Toyama M** 2023 Diversity and composition of flower-visiting insects and related factors in three fruit tree species. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 11: e100955. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.11.e100955>
- Nath R, Singh H and Mukherjee S** 2023 Insect pollinators decline: an emerging concern of Anthropocene epoch. *Journal of Apicultural Research* 62: 23–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00218839.2022.2088931>
- Nayak RK, Rana K, Prajapat KL and Gurjar MK** 2022 Insect pollinators of kiwifruit (*Actinidia deliciosa* Chev.) and flora of bumblebee (*Bombus haemorrhoidalis* Smith) in Solan region of Himachal Pradesh. *The Pharma Innovation Journal* 11: 1616–1619. <https://www.thepharmajournal.com/archives/2022/vol11issue2S/PartT/S-11-1-309-835.pdf>
- Nayduch D, Neupane S, Pickens V, Purvis T and Olds C** 2023 House flies are underappreciated yet important reservoirs and vectors of microbial threats to animal and human health. *Microorganisms* 11: 583. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11030583>
- Nelson W, Evans L, Donovan B and Howlett B** 2022 *Lasioglossum* bees – the forgotten pollinators. *Journal of Apicultural Research*: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00218839.2022.2028966>
- Nelson WR, Broussard MA and Howlett BG** 2024 Five steps for practice change in ecological and economic landscapes. *The Wētā* 57: 61–68. <https://weta.ento.org.nz/index.php/weta/article/view/423>

- Nicholas S, Thyselius M, Holden M and Nordström K** 2018 Rearing and long-term maintenance of *Eristalis tenax* hoverflies for research studies. *Journal of Visualized Experiments*: 57 711. <https://doi.org/10.3791/57711>
- Njue NI, Muthomi JW, Chemining'wa GN, Nderitu JH, Achieng J and Odanga JJ** 2023 Diversity of insect flower visitors on macadamia within a monoculture orchard in Murang'a County, Central Kenya. *Advances in Entomology* 11: 239–255. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ae.2023.114017>
- Nye WP and Anderson JL** 1974 Insect pollinators frequenting strawberry blossoms and the effect of honey bees on yield and fruit quality. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science* 99: 40–44. <https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.99.1.40>
- Okamoto K, Notoyama A, Muramatsu Y, Kagawa K, Mikawa Y, Aizawa M, Sueyoshi M, Mita T, Toyama M and Sonoda S** 2024 Pollination efficiency of *Apis mellifera* (Hymenoptera: Apidae), solitary bees (Hymenoptera), and flies (Diptera) in an insect-pollinated Japanese pear orchard. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology* 27: 102 242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aspen.2024.102242>
- Okello EN, Amugune NO, Mukiyama TK and Lattorff HMG** 2021 Abundance and community composition of flower visiting insects of avocado (*Persea americana* Mill) in the East African region. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science* 41: 2821–2827. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-021-00463-1>
- Oldham N, Herold J, Moulton K, Gonzalez A and Russo L** 2025 Contrasting effects of land-use and local disturbance on plant and pollinator communities in wetlands. *Basic and Applied Ecology*: S1439 179 125 000 635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2025.08.004>
- Orford KA, Vaughan IP and Memmott J** 2015 The forgotten flies: the importance of non-syrphid Diptera as pollinators. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 282: 20 142 934–20 142 934. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2014.2934>
- Osterman J, Aizen MA, Biesmeijer JC, Bosch J, Howlett BG, Inouye DW, Jung C, Martins DJ, Medel R, Pauw A, Seymour CL and Paxton RJ** 2021a Global trends in the number and diversity of managed pollinator species. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 322: 107 653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107653>
- Osterman J, Landaverde-González P, Garratt MPD, Gee M, Mandelik Y, Langowska A, Miñarro M, Cole LJ, Eraerts M, Bevk D, Avrech O, Koltowski Z, Trujillo-Elisea FI, Paxton RJ, Boreux V, Seymour CL and Howlett BG** 2021b On-farm experiences shape farmer knowledge, perceptions of pollinators, and management practices. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 32: e01949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2021.e01949>
- Otto CR, Graves TA, Robertson-Thompson D, Pearse I, Thogmartin WE, Murphy C, Webb L, Droege S, Steinkamp M and Grundel R** 2025 USGS pollinator science strategy 2025–2035—a review and look forward. p. 26. Circular, United States Geological Survey, Reston, Virginia, USA <http://dx.doi.org/10.3133/cir1556>
- Pain S** 2021 The essential fly. *Knowable Magazine* <https://knowablemagazine.org/article/food-environment/2021/the-essential-fly>
- Pascacio-Villafán C and Cohen AC** 2023 How rearing systems for various species of flies benefit humanity. *Insects* 14: 553. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects14060553>
- Pekas A, De Craecker I, Boonen S, Wäckers FL and Moerkens R** 2020 One stone; two birds: Concurrent pest control and pollination services provided by aphidophagous hoverflies. *Biological Control*: 104 328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2020.104328>
- Pérez-Balam J, Quezada-Euán JJG, Alfaro-Bates R, Medina S, McKendrick L, Soro A and Paxton RJ** 2012 The contribution of honey bees, flies and wasps to avocado (*Persea americana*) pollination in southern Mexico. *Journal of Pollination Ecology* 8: 42–47. [https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603\(2012\)6](https://doi.org/10.26786/1920-7603(2012)6)
- Pfiester M and Kaufman PE** 2009 Drone fly, rat-tailed maggot *Eristalis tenax* (Linnaeus) (Insecta: Diptera: Syrphidae). *EDIS* 2009: 7. <https://doi.org/10.32473/edis-in809-2009>
- Phillips BB, Williams A, Osborne JL and Shaw RF** 2018 Shared traits make flies and bees effective pollinators of oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L.). *Basic and Applied Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2018.06.004>
- Polyfly** 2019 Polyfly. <http://polyfly.es/en/> Accessed 20/4/2024
- Potts SG, Bartomeus I, Biesmeijer K, Breeze T, Casino A, Dauber J, Dieker P, Hochkirch A, Høye T and Isaac N** 2024 Refined proposal for an EU pollinator monitoring scheme. *Publications Office of the European Union*: 327. <https://doi.org/10.2760/2005545>
- Potts SG, Biesmeijer JC, Kremen C, Neumann P, Schweiger O and Kunin WE** 2010 Global pollinator declines: trends, impacts and drivers. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 25: 345–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2010.01.007>
- Prendergast KS, Garcia JE, Howard SR, Ren Z-X, McFarlane SJ and Dyer AG** 2021 Bee representations in human art and culture through the ages. *Art & Perception* 10: 1–62. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134913-bja10031>

- Prokop P, Molnárová D, Fančovičová J and Medina-Jerez W** 2021 Seasonal variability in flower lifespan in common chicory (*Cichorium intybus* L.). *Flora* 284: 151935. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flora.2021.151935>
- Quinet M and Jacquemart. A-L** 2017 Cultivar placement affects pollination efficiency and fruit production in European pear (*Pyrus communis*) orchards. *European Journal of Agronomy* 91: 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2017.09.015>
- Rader R, Bartomeus I, Garibaldi LA, Garratt MPD, Howlett BG, Winfree R, Cunningham SA, Mayfield MM, Arthur AD, Andersson GKS, Bommarco R, Brittain C, Carvalheiro LG, Chacoff NP, Entling MH, Foully B, Freitas BM, Gemmill-Herren B, Ghazoul J, Griffin SR, Gross CL, Herbertsson L, Herzog F, Hipólito J, Jaggar S, Jauker F, Klein A-M, Kleijn D, Krishnan S, Lemos CQ, Lindström SAM, Mandelik Y, Monteiro VM, Nelson W, Nilsson L, Pattemore DE, de O. Pereira N, Pisanty G, Potts SG, Reemer M, Rundlöf M, Sheffield CS, Scheper J, Schüepp C, Smith HG, Stanley DA, Stout JC, Szentgyörgyi H, Taki H, Vergara CH, Viana BF and Woyciechowski M** 2016 Non-bee insects are important contributors to global crop pollination. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113: 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1517092112>
- Rader R, Cunningham SA, Howlett BG and Inouye DW** 2020 Non-bee insects as visitors and pollinators of crops: biology, ecology and management. *Annual Review of Entomology* 65: 391–407. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-011019-025055>
- Rader R, Edwards W, Westcott DA, Cunningham SA and Howlett BG** 2013 Diurnal effectiveness of pollination by bees and flies in agricultural *Brassica rapa*: Implications for ecosystem resilience. *Basic and Applied Ecology* 14: 20–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2012.10.011>
- Rader R, Howlett BG, Cunningham SA, Westcott DA, Newstrom-Lloyd LE, Walker MK, Teulon DAJ and Edwards W** 2009 Alternative pollinator taxa are equally efficient but not as effective as the honeybee in a mass flowering crop. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 46: 1080–1087. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2009.01700.x>
- Raguso RA** 2020 Don't forget the flies: Dipteran diversity and its consequences for floral ecology and evolution. *Applied Entomology and Zoology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13355-020-00668-9>
- Rahimi E and Jung C** 2025 Trends in pollination scientists' research: a comprehensive analysis in citations and research topics. *Ecology and Evolution* 15: e71215. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.71215>
- Rangel J, Lau P, Strauss B, Hildinger E, Hernandez B, Rodriguez S, Bryant V and Tarone AM** 2023 Pollen associated with a Texas population of blow flies (Diptera: Calliphoridae) highlights underappreciated aspects of their biology. *Ecological Entomology*: een.13298. <https://doi.org/10.1111/een.13298>
- Reilly J, Bartomeus I, Simpson D, Allen-Perkins A, Garibaldi L and Winfree R** 2024 Wild insects and honey bees are equally important to crop yields in a global analysis. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*: e13843. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13843>
- Requier F, Pérez-Méndez N, Andersson GKS, Blareau E, Merle I and Garibaldi LA** 2023 Bee and non-bee pollinator importance for local food security. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 38: 196–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2022.10.006>
- Reynolds SK, Clem CS, Fitz-Gerald B and Young AD** 2024 A comprehensive review of long-distance hover fly migration (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Ecological Entomology*: een.13373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/een.13373>
- Richard E, Braukmann T, Raine N and Steinke D** 2024 A little-known world - assessing a non-bee crop flower visiting community using metabarcoding. Authorea, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.171182026.67417474/v1>
- Robertson AR, Finch JTD, Young AD, Spooner-Hart RN, Outim SKM and Cook JM** 2020 Species diversity in bee flies and hover flies (Diptera: Bombyliidae and Syrphidae) in the horticultural environments of the Blue Mountains, Australia. *Austral Entomology* 59: 561–571. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aen.12483>
- Rogers EKB, Franklin D and Voss SC** 2020 Dietary effects on the development of *Calliphora dubia* and *Chrysomya rufifacies* (Diptera: Calliphoridae): implications for postmortem interval. *Journal of Medical Entomology*: tjaa142. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jme/tjaa142>
- Rollin O and Garibaldi LA** 2019 Impacts of honeybee density on crop yield: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 56: 1152–1163. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13355>
- Rotheray GE** 1993 Colour guide to hoverfly larvae (Diptera, Syrphidae) in Britain and Europe. *Dipterists Digest* 1, 9: 155. https://diptera.info/downloads/df_1_9_Colour_Guide_to%20Hoverfly_Larvae.pdf
- Rustiawan A and Rifai M** 2022 Local wisdom fly trap effectiveness in the culinary area of Bantul beach tourism, Yogyakarta. *Epidemiology and Society Health Review (ESHR)* 4: 54–60. <https://doi.org/10.26555/eshr.v4i2.5529>
- Saeed S, Naqqash MN, Jaleel W, Saeed Q and Ghouri F** 2016 The effect of blow flies (Diptera: Calliphoridae) on the size and weight of mangos (*Mangifera indica* L.). *PeerJ* 4: e2076. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.2076>
- Saeed S, Sajjad A, Kwon O and Kwon YJ** 2008 Fidelity of Hymenoptera and Diptera pollinators in onion (*Allium cepa* L.) pollination. *Entomological Research* 38: 276–280. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1748-5967.2008.00187.x>

- Sagwe RN, Peters MK, Dubois T, Steffan-Dewenter I and Lattorff HMG** 2022 Pollinator efficiency of avocado (*Persea americana*) flower insect visitors. *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12178>
- Sahib S, Driauch O and Belqat B** 2020 New data on the hoverflies of Morocco (Diptera, Syrphidae) with faunistic and bibliographical inventories. *ZooKeys* 971: 59–103. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.971.49416>
- Sajjad A and Saeed S** 2010 Floral host plant range of syrphid flies (Syrphidae: Diptera) under natural conditions in Southern Punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Botany* 42: 1187–1200. [https://mail.pakbs.org/pjbot/PDFs/42\(2\)/PJB42\(2\)1187.pdf](https://mail.pakbs.org/pjbot/PDFs/42(2)/PJB42(2)1187.pdf)
- Sakurai A and Takahashi K** 2017 Flowering phenology and reproduction of the *Solidago virgaurea* L. complex along an elevational gradient on Mt Norikura, central Japan. *Plant Species Biology* 32: 270–278. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1442-1984.12153>
- Sánchez M, Abreu AC, Tristán AI, Velásquez Y, Fernández I and Cuevas J** 2024 Floral attractants and rewards to pollinators in *Mangifera indica* L. *Scientia Horticulturae* 332: 113–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2024.113180>
- Sánchez M, Belliure B, Montserrat M, Gil J and Velásquez Y** 2022a Pollination by the hoverfly *Eristalinus aeneus* (Diptera: Syrphidae) in two hybrid seed crops: celery and fennel (Apiaceae). *The Journal of Agricultural Science* 160: 194–206. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859622000314>
- Sánchez M, Velásquez Y, González M and Cuevas J** 2022b Activity and foraging behaviour of the hoverfly *Eristalinus aeneus* (Scopoli, 1763) in protected cultivation of mango (*Mangifera indica* L.). *Bulletin of Entomological Research* 112: 101–109. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007485321000717>
- Sánchez M, Velásquez Y, González M and Cuevas J** 2022c Hoverfly pollination enhances yield and fruit quality in mango under protected cultivation. *Scientia Horticulturae* 304: 111–1320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2022.111320>
- Sánchez M, Velásquez Y, González M and Cuevas J** 2022d Pollination effectiveness of the hoverfly *Eristalinus aeneus* (Scopoli, 1763) in diploid and triploid associated watermelon crop. *Insects* 13: 1021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects13111021>
- Sánchez M, Velásquez Y, Vaez-Olivera M, González M and Cuevas J** 2018 Sírfidos (Diptera: Syrphidae): aliados en la polinización del cultivo protegido del mango (*Mangifera indica* L.). *Agrícola Vergel* 409: 1. https://www.edicioneslav.es/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/AGR%C3%8DCOLA-VERGEL-N%C3%BAm-409_M.-S%C3%A1nchez.pdf
- Saunders ME** 2018 Insect pollinators collect pollen from wind-pollinated plants: implications for pollination ecology and sustainable agriculture. *Insect Conservation and Diversity* 11: 13–31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12243>
- Saunders ME and Rader R** 2019 Network modularity influences plant reproduction in a mosaic tropical agroecosystem. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 286: 20190296. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2019.0296>
- Schirmel J, Albrecht M, Bauer P-M, Sutter L, Pfister SC and Entling MH** 2018 Landscape complexity promotes hoverflies across different types of semi-natural habitats in farmland. *Journal of Applied Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13095>
- Schittenhelm S, Giadis T and Rao VR** 1997 Efficiency of various insects in germplasm regeneration of carrot, onion and turnip rape accessions. *Plant Breeding* 116: 369–375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0523.1997.tb01014.x>
- Shao J, Quan Q, Cai W, Guan L and Wu W** 2012 The effect of floral morphology on seed set in *Carthamus tinctorius* Linnaeus (Asteraceae) clones of Sichuan province in China. *Plant Systematics and Evolution* 298: 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00606-011-0523-2>
- Sheffield CS** 2013 Native pollinators and the diversity of bees. *Journal of the Entomological Society of British Columbia* 110: 41. <https://journal.entsocbc.ca/index.php/journal/article/view/853/877>
- Shimomae K, Sato T, Yuichi Y, Naing SS and Miyatake T** 2022 Longevity of *Lucilia sericata* (Meigen, 1826) used as pollinator. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology* 25: 101–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aspen.2022.101999>
- Singh G** 1997 Pollination, pollinators and fruit setting in mango. *Acta Horticulturae*: 116–123. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1997.455.16>
- Sisterson MS, Dwyer DP and Uchima SY** 2020 Insect diversity in vineyards, almond orchards, olive orchards, alfalfa fields, and pastures in the San Joaquin Valley of California. *Journal of Insect Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-020-00250-2>
- Siviter H, Fisher A, Baer B, Brown MJF, Camargo IF, Cole J, Le Conte Y, Dorin B, Evans JD, Farina W, Fine J, Fischer LR, Garratt MPD, Giannini TC, Giray T, Li-Byarlay H, López-Urbe MM, Nieh JC, Przybyla K, Raine NE, Ray AM, Singh G, Spivak M, Traynor K, Kapheim KM and Harrison JF** 2023 Protecting pollinators and our food supply: understanding and managing threats to pollinator health. *Insectes Sociaux* 70: 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-022-00897-x>

- Skaldina O and Blande JD** 2025 Global biases in ecology and conservation research: insight from pollinator studies. *Ecology Letters* 28: e70 050. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.70050>
- Smith TJ and Saunders ME** 2016 Honey bees: the queens of mass media, despite minority rule among insect pollinators. *Insect Conservation and Diversity* 9: 384–390. <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12178>
- Sonoda S, Kagawa K, Furui Y, Nakada K, Koyama M, Toda S, Sugiura N, Nakamura S, Sueyoshi M, Mita T and Toyama M** 2022 Mutual complementarity among diverse pollinators as a mechanism underlying open insect pollination in Japanese pear orchards. *Journal of Applied Entomology* 146: 498–510. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jen.12967>
- Souther SK, Sandor ME, Sample M, Gabrielson S and Aslan CE** 2024 Bee and butterfly records indicate diversity losses in western and southern North America, but extensive knowledge gaps remain. *PLOS ONE* 19: e0289742. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0289742>
- Sowa G, Droge STJ, Sousa JP and Maltby L** 2025 Arthropod biodiversity in European crops: representative taxa for pest control and pollination. *Ecological Indicators* 178: 114080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.114080>
- Ssymank A and Kearns CA** 2009 Flies - pollinators on two wings. *Caring for pollinators* pp. 39–52. Bundesamt für Naturschutz (BfN, Bonn <https://www.bfn.de/publikationen/bfn-schriften/bfn-schriften-250-caring-pollinators-safeguarding-agro-biodiversity-and>
- Ssymank A, Kearns CA, Pape T and Thompson FC** 2008 Pollinating flies (Diptera): A major contribution to plant diversity and agricultural production. *Biodiversity* 9: 86–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14888386.2008.9712892>
- Stavert JR, Liñán-Cembrano G, Beggs JR, Howlett BG, Pattemore DE and Bartomeus I** 2016 Hairiness: the missing link between pollinators and pollination. *PeerJ* 4 (e2779): 18 pp. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.2779>
- Stavert JR, Pattemore DE, Bartomeus I, Gaskett AC and Beggs JR** 2018 Exotic flies maintain pollination services as native pollinators decline with agricultural expansion. *Journal of Applied Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13103>
- Sung I-H, Lin M-Y, Chang C-H, Cheng A-S and Chen W-S** 2006 Pollinators and their behaviors on mango flowers in Southern Taiwan. *Formosan Entomologist* 26: 161–170. <https://doi.org/10.6661/TESE.2006013>
- Tatsuno M, Sueyoshi M and Osawa N** 2023 Pollination ecology of the early-spring-blooming dioecious shrub *Eurya japonica* (Pentaphylacaceae). *Botany: cjb-2022-0083*. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjb-2022-0083>
- Tavares JM, Villalobos EM and Wright MG** 2015 Contribution of insect pollination to *Macadamia integrifolia* production in Hawaii. *Proceedings of the Hawaiian Entomological Society* 47: 35–49. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/38671>
- Timberlake TP, Cirtwill AR, Sapkota S, Bhusal DR, Devkota K, Karki R, Joshi D, Saville NM, Kortsch S, Baral S, Roslin T and Memmott J** 2024 Agricultural specialisation increases the vulnerability of pollination services for smallholder farmers. *Journal of Applied Ecology*: 1365-2664.14732. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14732>
- Tiusanen M, Hebert PDN, Schmidt NM and Roslin T** 2016 One fly to rule them all—muscid flies are the key pollinators in the Arctic. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 283: 20161271. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2016.1271>
- Toikkanen J, Halme P, Kahanpää J and Toivonen M** 2022 Effects of landscape composition on hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) in mass-flowering crop fields within forest-dominated landscapes. *Journal of Insect Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-022-00436-w>
- Toivonen M, Herzon I, Rajanen H, Toikkanen J and Kuussaari M** 2019 Late flowering time enhances insect pollination of turnip rape. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 56: 1164–1175. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13349>
- Toivonen M, Karimaa A-E, Herzon I and Kuussaari M** 2022 Flies are important pollinators of mass-flowering caraway and respond to landscape and floral factors differently from honeybees. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 323: 107698. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107698>
- Toukem NK, Dubois T, Mohamed SA, Lattorff HMG, Jordaens K and Yusuf AA** 2023 The effect of annual flower strips on pollinator visitation and fruit set of avocado (*Persea americana* Mill.) in Kenya. *Arthropod-Plant Interactions* 17: 19–29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11829-022-09939-4>
- Upchurch A, Spurr CJ, Quarrell SR, Rowbottom RM and Allen GR** 2023 Toward optimising reproductive output of *Eristalis tenax* (Diptera: Syrphidae) for commercial mass rearing systems. *Austral Entomology* 62: 360–371. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aen.12660>
- Van Steenis J** 2023 Saprophytic breeding sites for hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae): from artificial design to natural habitat management. *Journal of Syrphidae* 2: 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.55710/1.DIOF2888>
- Varelas** 2019 Food wastes as a potential new source for edible insect mass production for food and feed: a review. *Fermentation* 5: 81. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation5030081>
- Vasiliev D** 2021 Implications of pollinator biodiversity decline for food security, economy, and pollinator conservation policies. *E3S Web of Conferences* 259: 01006. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202125901006>

- Villa-Galaviz E, Cirtwill AR, Gibson R, Timberlake T, Roslin T and Memmott J** 2023 What makes a good pollinator? Abundant and specialised insects with long flight periods transport the most strawberry pollen. *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 4: e12253. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12253>
- Vinogradova E** 2009 Effect of food and temperature on the reproduction of the blowfly, *Calliphora vicina* R.-D. (Diptera, Calliphoridae), a popular model object in biological research. *Entomological Review* 89: 137–142. <https://doi.org/10.1134/s001387380902002x>
- Westerkamp C and Gottsberger G** 2000 Diversity pays in crop pollination. *Crop Science* 40: 1209. <https://doi.org/10.2135/cropsci2000.4051209x>
- Williams GR, Tarypy DR, vanEngelsdorp D, Chauzat M-P, Cox-Foster DL, Delaplane KS, Neumann P, Pettis JS, Rogers REL and Shutler D** 2010 Colony collapse disorder in context. *BioEssays* 32: 845–846. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bies.201000075>
- Wittische J, Lippert S, Luttringer A, Arieu H, Cruz A, Andrasi B, Thissen D, Schleimer A, Drygala F, Mehnert J, Mengual X, Cantú-Salazar L and Frantz AC** 2024 High genetic connectivity of two pollinating flies despite urban disturbance. *Ecosphere* 15: e4784. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.4784>
- Zattara EE and Aizen MA** 2021 Worldwide occurrence records suggest a global decline in bee species richness. *One Earth* 4: 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.12.005>
- Zheng JJ, Janderova ZM and Lang JD** 2024 *Eristalis tenax* movement behavior in response to light, temperature, and food. *Georgia journal of science* 82: 1–19. <https://digitalcommons.gaacademy.org/gjs/vol82/iss2/1>
- Ziółkowska E, Walczyńska A and Topping CJ** 2025 The Formal Model for the hoverfly *Eristalis tenax* (Diptera, Syrphidae) agent-based model in the Animal Landscape and Man Simulation System (ALMaSS). *Food and Ecological Systems Modelling* 6. <https://doi.org/0.3897/fmj.6.152847>
- Zoller L, Bennett J and Knight TM** 2023 Plant–pollinator network change across a century in the subarctic. *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 7: 102–112. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01928-3>